

2024	Fauna Balkana University of Novi Sad, Serbia	Volume 5 pp 1-30
------	---	---------------------

Millipedes (Arthropoda: Myriapoda: Diplopoda) of Mt. Avala, Serbia

MIRKO ŠEVIĆ^{1,2*},
SLOBODAN MAKAROV^{1,2}

¹University of Belgrade – Faculty of Biology, Institute of Zoology, Studentski Trg 16, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia

²Serbian Biospeleological Society, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 2, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

*e-mail: mirko.sevic@bio.bg.ac.rs

SUMMARY. This paper presents a faunistic review of the millipedes of Mt. Avala, located near Belgrade, Serbia. It is the first thorough study of millipedes at the local level, combining freshly collected material, material from collections, and published data. In total, the millipede fauna of Mt. Avala comprises 25 confirmed species from 18 genera and 11 families in seven orders. The two families with the largest number of species are Julidae (eight species) and Polydesmidae (seven species). The family Glomeridae includes two representatives, while the other eight families, namely Polyxenidae, Polyzoniidae, Chordeumatidae, Mastigophorophyllidae, Craspedosomatidae, Verhoeffiidae, Dorypetalidae and Paradoxosomatidae, are each represented by a single species. It is particularly noteworthy that the family Verhoeffiidae was discovered for the first time in Serbia with the species *Haplogona oculodistincta* (Verhoeff, 1893). Four species previously listed for Mt. Avala have been removed from the list, namely *Polyxenus lagurus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Julus terrestris* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Pachyiulus cattarensis* (Latzel, 1884), and *Unciger foetidus* (C.L. Koch, 1838). The millipede fauna of Mt. Avala belongs mainly to the Central-Southeast European, Central-East-Southeast European, and Southeast European fauna. Photographs of living specimens of most species inhabiting the territory of Mt. Avala are provided, along with a map of all localities where the specimens were collected

KEY WORDS: Belgrade, faunistic diversity, Pannonian Basin, zoogeography.

INTRODUCTION

Mountain Avala is situated 12 km from Belgrade and covers an area of about 10 km². Positioned on the southern margin of the Pannonian Basin, a border zone between the uplifted unities of the Dinarides and the Carpathian-Balkanides (Rundić et al. 2019). Geologically, Mt. Avala predominantly consists of Jurassic carbonates, an ophiolite mélange, and Cretaceous sediments (Bragin et al. 2011). Much later, different Miocene and Quaternary sedimentary units partially covered basement rocks (Rundić et al. 2019). During the middle and late Miocene, Mt. Avala was a central part of a large island in the central Paratethys Sea, along with parts of Belgrade and Mt. Kosmaj (Rundić and Knežević 2017). Characterized by a diverse and specific pedological structure, this mountain is extremely rich in vegetation and floristic elements. The flora of Mt. Avala numbers around 600 plant species; the mountain is mostly covered by forest vegetation, mainly by oak (*Quercus*) and beech (*Fagus*), alongside a few scattered meadows and plantations of allochthonous species (Borisavljević et al. 1955; Sabovljević and Cvetić 2003).

The first information about Diplopoda in Serbia dates from the late 19th century, when seven species were mentioned by Latzel (1882, 1884). During the 20th century, more papers were published, first by Attems (1929, 1959), followed by Strasser (1971) and Mršić (1985). At the end of the 20th and beginning of the 21st century, many papers were published that treated the fauna of millipedes in Serbia (e.g., Ćurčić and Makarov 1997, 1998; Makarov et al. 2002, 2003, 2004), raising the number of known species in Serbia to 80. Antić et al. (2013) published the last comprehensive list, compiling all previously published records as well as unpublished data, topping off the number of known species of Diplopoda at 100. Today the number of millipedes recorded in Serbia has risen to around 110 (Antić et al. 2021; Šević et al. 2022).

Although Mt. Avala is near the city of Belgrade, no published papers are focusing on the diplopod fauna of Mt. Avala in particular. This locality has been mentioned in several studies, albeit within the broader context of millipede fauna in Serbia or the Former Yugoslavia (see Tomić-Jovanović 1964; Mršić 1988; Makarov et al. 2004). The objective of the current study is to systematically review existing knowledge concerning the biodiversity of diplopods on Mount Avala, combining freshly collected specimens, specimens from the IZB collection (see below), and published data to provide a unique list of species with their zoogeographical affiliation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Samples were collected using both active and passive methods. Active methods

consisted of collecting individual specimens by hand or using a leaf litter sieve with grid openings of 10 x 10 mm. Passive methods consisted of two MSS traps set up according to Lopez and Oromi (2010). The material analyzed here is preserved in 70% ethanol and deposited in the collection of the Institute of Zoology, University of Belgrade – Faculty of Biology (IZB). Specimens were examined and dissected using a Nikon SMZ 745T stereomicroscope. The map was made using Google Earth Pro, version 7.3.4, and modified in Adobe Photoshop CS6. *In situ* pictures were made using an Olympus Stylus Tough TG-6 Camera. The list of species follows the classification of Enghoff et al. (2015) with slight modifications. For each species, the general distribution is given, along with the original name combination and synonyms following Kime and Enghoff (2011, 2017, 2021) with some modifications.

Further, the published data are given for each species that was previously registered on Mt. Avala. If only “Avala” is specified for a species in the literature, we have marked the data with “Without precise locality”. Finally, chorotypes are designated for all species following the chorotype proposals of Vigna Taglianti et al. (1999) with some modifications to match their distribution as closely as possible. The following abbreviations are used for zoogeographical categories: CEE – Central-East European; CES – Central-East-Southeast European; CSE – Central-Southeast European; DIN – Dinaric; EUR – European; SEE – Southeast European; TEM – Turano-Eastern Mediterranean.

LOCALITIES

Here we give a short overview of the localities (Fig. 1) from which the specimens were collected:

AV01: [44.6840N, 20.5276E] Zuce, Duboki Potok [Deep Creek], 285 m a.s.l., *Quercus* forest, deep leaf litter in the ravines.

AV02: [44.6883N, 20.5289E] Zuce, Gleđevac, 336 m a.s.l., predominantly *Quercus* forest, with *Acer* and *Crataegus*.

AV03: [44.6852N, 20.5307E] Zuce, Gleđevac, 295 m a.s.l., *Abies* plantation.

AV04: [44.6940N, 20.5219E] Beli Potok, Čarapićev Brest, 294 m a.s.l., *Fagus* forest with a creek running through, in leaf litter.

AV05: [44.6877N, 20.5075E] Pinosava, 331 m a.s.l., two MSS traps.

AV06: [44.7011N, 20.5176E] Beli Potok, 285 m a.s.l., in moss, close to the Kamenac spring.

AV07: [44.7007N, 20.5203E] Road from Beli Potok to Čarapićev Brest, 300 m a.s.l., near the road, bushes of *Robinia* and *Prunus*.

AV08: [44.6948N, 20.5160E] Beli Potok, 400 m a.s.l., underneath the Avala tower base *Fagus* forest with a few scattered *Quercus* trees.

Fig. 1. Mt. Avala with localities where millipede specimens were collected.

AV09: [44.6819N, 20.5192E] Ripanj, 323 m a.s.l., “forester’s house”, *Pinus* plantation, with some *Quercus* trees.

AV10: [44.6833N, 20.5178E] Ripanj, near forester’s house, 307 m a.s.l., *Fagus* forest, in rotting logs and thick leaf litter in the ravines.

AV11: [44.6866N, 20.5103E] Monument to Soviet War Veterans, Ripanj, 330 m. a.s.l. *Quercus* and *Fagus* forest, the ground covered by *Hedera*.

AV12: [44.6877N, 20.5121E] Monument to Soviet War Veterans, Ripanj, 420 m a.s.l., *Quercus* and *Fagus*, around and under fallen logs.

AV13: [44.6887N, 20.5136E] Monument to Soviet War Veterans, Ripanj, 428 m a.s.l., *Quercus* and *Fagus* forest.

AV14: [44.6883N, 20.5226E] Zuce, locality Duboki Potok, at 338 m a.s.l., *Fagus* forest.

AV15: [44.6888N, 20.5226E] Zuce, the remains of old Roman mines, 370 m a.s.l., *Quercus* and *Fagus* forest, rocky ground covered with leaf litter and common *Hedera*.

AV16: [44.6902N, 20.5096E] Pinosava, 261 m a.s.l., *Fagus* forest.

AV17: [44.6883N, 20.5086E] Pinosava, 365 m a.s.l., *Pinus* plantation.

AV18: [44.6890N, 20.5095E] Pinosava, 398 m a.s.l., *Fagus* forest.

AV19: [44.6986N, 20.5081E] Between Beli Potok and Pinosava, 325 m a.s.l., along the road, in thick layers of leaf litter, *Fagus* forest.

AV20: [44.6982N, 20.5111E] Beli Potok, 379 m a.s.l., *Fagus* forest, in fallen logs overgrown with *Hedera*.

AV21: [44.6941N, 20.5235E] Vranevac stream, Beli Potok, 308 m a.s.l., in remains of ephemeral stream, with rocky sides, *Fagus* forest.

AV22: [44.6933N, 20.5259E] Beli Potok village, at 300 m a.s.l., thick plantation of *Robinia*.

AV23: [44.6933N, 20.5235E] Beli Potok, at 305 m a.s.l., mixed *Quercus* and *Fagus* forest with *Hedera*.

AV24: [44.6895N, 20.5034E] Road to Ripanj village, 214 m a.s.l., *Quercus* forest, near the ruined water spring.

AV25: [44.6936N, 20.5073E] Pinosava, 327 m a.s.l. near spring Sakinac, *Fagus* forest, in leaf litter.

RESULTS

Polyxenida VERHOEFF, 1934

Family Polyxenidae Lucas, 1840

1. *Propolyxenus argentifer* (Verhoeff, 1921) Fig. 2A

Polyxenus argentifer Verhoeff, 1921: 47–49, fig. 38.

Polyxenus trivittatus Verhoeff, 1941: 297 [synonymized under *Propolyxenus argentifer* by Short et al. (2020: 313)].

Propolyxenus argentifer—Short et al. (2020: 313–320).

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV04:** 1 specimen, 1.10.1995., leg. S. Makarov; 17 specimens, 04.03.2021., leg. D. Antić, M. Šević; **AV11:** 2 specimens, 14.03.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV12:** 1 specimen, 27.03.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV13:** 6 specimens, 06.02.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV20:** 4 specimens, 16.05.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV23:** 1 specimen, 27.06.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV24:** 34 specimens, 23.05.1993., leg. S. Makarov.

DISTRIBUTION: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Croatia, Georgia, Greece, Iran, Israel, Romania, Russia (Krasnodar Krai), Serbia, Turkey, Ukraine (Kime and Enghoff 2011: 20; Short et al. 2020).

CHOROTYPE: TEM.

Fig. 2. Representatives of Polyxenida, Glomerida, Polyzoniida and Chordeumatida from Mt. Avala. **A**, *Propolyxenus argentifer* (Verhoeff, 1921); **B**, *Glomeris hexasticha* Brandt, 1833; **C**, *Trachysphaera schmidtii* Heller, 1858; **D**, *Polyzonium germanicum* Brandt, 1837; **E**, *Haplogona oculodistincta* (Verhoeff, 1893); **F**, *Mastigona bosniensis* (Verhoeff, 1987); **G**, *Craspedosoma raulinsii* Leach, 1814. Photos by Dragan Antić.

REMARKS: Makarov et al. (2004) reported *Polyxenus lagurus* (Linnaeus, 1758) from Mt. Avala, but based on examination of the specimens from the IZB collection and freshly collected material we concluded that all of them belong to *Propolyxenus argentifer*.

Glomerida BRANDT, 1833

Family Glomeridae Leach, 1816

2. *Glomeris hexasticha* Brandt, 1833 Fig. 2B

Glomeris hexasticha Brandt, 1833: 197.

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV10**: 1 juv, 14.03.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV15**: 1♀, 10.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković, B. Stojanović; **AV16**: 1♂, 1 juv, 24.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić; **AV20**: 1♀, 16.05.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV23**: 1 juv, 27.06.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić.

DISTRIBUTION: Albania, Austria, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Moldova, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovenia, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine (Kime and Enghoff 2011: 27).

PUBLISHED DATA: Without precise locality (Tomić-Jovanović 1964).

CHOROTYPE: CES.

3. *Trachysphaera schmidtii* Heller, 1858 Fig. 2C

Trachysphaera Schmidtii (sic!) Heller, 1858: 317, figs 1–6.

Gervaisia noduligera Verhoeff, 1906: 812, 815, 819, figs 14, 17, 18 [synonymized by Sillaber (1987: 181)].

Gervaisia illyrica Verhoeff, 1908: 531, 534, figs 2, 12, 13 [synonymized with a question mark (?) under *T. noduligera* by Strasser and Minelli (1984: 198), later appeared in the synonym lists of *T. noduligera* by Foddai et al. (1995: 12)].

Gervaisia costata var. *acutula* Latzel, 1884: 89, figs 41, 42 [synonymized under *T. schmidtii* by Antić et al. (2021: 286, fig. 8)].

Gervaisia multiclavigera Verhoeff, 1898a: 163–165, figs 5–7, 9, 10 [synonymized under *T. schmidtii* by Antić et al. (2021: 286, fig. 8)].

Gervaisia cultrifera Verhoeff, 1906: 810, 815, 816, 820, 821 [synonymized under *T. schmidtii* by Antić et al. (2021: 286, fig. 8)].

DISTRIBUTION: Albania, Austria, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Croatia, Hungary, Italy, North Macedonia, Serbia, Switzerland (Kime and Enghoff 2011: 38; Antić et al. 2021).

PUBLISHED DATA: Čarapićev Brest (**AV04**) (Antić et al. 2021).

CHOROTYPE: CSE.

REMARKS: A widespread species in Serbia previously misidentified as *Trachysphaera costata* (Waga, 1857) (Antić et al. 2021).

Polyzoniida Cook, 1895

Family Polyzoniidae Newport, 1844

4. *Polyzonium germanicum* Brandt, 1837 Fig. 2D

Polyzonium germanicum Brandt, 1837: 179.

Polyzonium bosniense Verhoeff, 1898a: 170–172, fig. 11 [synonymized under *P. germanicum* by Shelley (1997: 26)].

Platyululus audouinianus Gervais, 1836: 435 [synonymized under *P. germanicum* by Brolemann (1935: 104)].

Polyzonium controversarium Verhoeff, 1937: 115, 116, figs 25–27 [synonymized under *P. germanicum* by Strasser (1969: 165)].

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV24**: 1♀, 1 juv, 24.08.1992., leg. S. Makarov.

DISTRIBUTION: Albania, Austria, Belarus, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Germany, Estonia, Finland, France, Great Britain, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Ukraine (Kime and Enghoff 2011: 42).

CHOROTYPE: EUR.

Chordeumatida Pocock, 1894

Family Chordeumatidae C. L. Koch, 1847

5. *Melogona broelemanni* Verhoeff, 1897

Microchordeuma (Chordeumella) broelemanni Verhoeff, 1897a: 152, 153, figs 4, 6.

Microchordeuma (Chordeumella) albanicum Verhoeff, 1901: 259, 260 fig. 8m [synonymized under *M. broelemanni* by Strasser (1976: 590)].

Chordeumella broelemanni auct.

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV04**: 8 juv, 1.10.1995., leg. S. Makarov; 1♂, 28.06.1995.; 1♀, 13.4.1996.; **AV07**: 1♂, 1♀, 06.02.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, M. Šević; **AV10** 1♀, 14.03.2021., leg. A. Marković; **AV16**: 1♀, 24.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV19**: 1♀, 16.05.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV20**: 1♀, 16.05.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić.

DISTRIBUTION: Albania, Austria, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech

Republic, Greece, Hungary, North Macedonia, Romania, Slovenia, Serbia (Kime and Enghoff 2021: 54).

PUBLISHED DATA: Čarapićev Brest (**AV04**) (Makarov et al. 2004).

CHOROTYPE: CSE.

Family Mastigophorophyllidae Verhoeff, 1899

6. *Mastigona bosniensis* (Verhoeff, 1897) Fig. 2F

Heteroporatia bosniense Verhoeff, 1897b: 134, 135.

Heteroporatia mehelyi Verhoeff, 1897b: 195, 196, figs 15–17 [synonymized under *M. bosniensis* by Korsós (1994: 33)].

Heteroporatia vihorlatica [synonymized under *M. bosniensis* by Hauser (2004a: 215–218, figs 1–3)].

Mastogona vihorlatica auct.

Mastigona mehelyi auct.

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV02**: 2♀♀, 21.11.2020., leg. D. Antić, D. Stojanović, A. Marković; **AV07**: 3♀♀, 06.02.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, M. Šević; **AV21**: 1 juv., 27.06.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV25**: 1♂, 31.10.2018., leg. B. Ilić.

DISTRIBUTION: Austria, Belarus, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia (Kaliningrad), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia (Kime and Enghoff 2021: 119).

CHOROTYPE: CES.

Family Craspedosomatidae Gray in Jones, 1843

7. *Craspedosoma raulinsii* Leach, 1814 Fig. 2G

Craspedosoma raulinsii Leach, 1814: 380.

Craspedosoma rawlinsii Leach, 1816: 380.

Craspedosoma simile Verhoeff, 1891: 128–130 figs 8, 9 [synonymized under *C. rawlinsi* by Schubart, (1964: 8, 9)].

Craspedosoma transsylvanicum Verhoeff, 1897b: 182, 183, figs 5, 6 [synonymized under *C. rawlinsii transsylvanicum* by Hauser (2001: 39, figs 13a–13d)].

Craspedosoma allemannicum Verhoeff, 1910: 39 fig. 2 [synonymized under *C. rawlinsii alemannicum* by Spelda (1991: 146)].

Craspedosoma suevicum Verhoeff, 1910: 39, 40 fig. 10 [synonymized under *C. rawlinsii germanicum* by Hauser (2004: 19)].

Craspedosoma wehranum Verhoeff, 1910: 40, figs 8, 9 [synonymized under *C. rawlinsii rawlinsii* by Hauser (2004: 19).

Craspedosoma vomrathi auct.

Craspedosoma germanicum auct.

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV04**: 1♂, 1♀, 21.11.2020., leg. D. Antić, D. Stojanović, A. Marković; 1♀, 4.3.2021., leg. D. Antić, M. Šević; **AV08**: 1♂, 06.02.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, M. Šević; **AV10**: 2♂♂, 14.03.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV21**: 2 juv, 27.06.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić.

DISTRIBUTION: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, France (Corsica), Germany, Great Britain, Great Britain (Northern Ireland), Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Russia (Kaliningrad), Serbia, Slovenia, Slovakia, Sweden; Introduced in North America (Kime and Enghoff 2021: 71).

CHOROTYPE: EUR.

REMARKS: A widespread species in Serbia, previously known under *C. transsylvanicum*.

Family Verhoeffiidae Verhoeff, 1899

8. *Haplogona oculodistincta* (Verhoeff, 1893) Fig. 2E

Chordeuma oculodistinctum Verhoeff, 1893: 269, 270.

Chordeuma graecense Attems, 1895: 197–200, taf. III, figs 40–52 [synonymized under *Verhoeffia oculodistincta* by Brölemann (1895: 459)]

Latzelia illyricum Verhoeff, 1895a: 210, 211 [synonymized under *Verhoeffia oculodistincta* by Brölemann (1895: 459)]

Haplogona oculodistincta—Cook and Collins (1895: 3)

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV05**: 1♂, 12.07.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV13**: 1♂, 06.02.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV25**: 1♂, 2♀♀, 11.11.2022., leg. J. Milovanović, B. Ilić, S. Ilić.

DISTRIBUTION: Austria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Italy, Serbia, Slovenia, Slovakia (Kime and Enghoff 2021: 141; present study).

CHOROTYPE: CES.

Remarks: This taxon and the family Verhoeffiidae are new to the fauna of Serbia.

Callipodida Pocock, 1894**Family Dorypetalidae Verhoeff, 1900****9. *Dorypetalum degenerans* (Latzel, 1884)***Lysiopetalum degenerans* Latzel, 1884: 218–221, fig. 112.

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV04**: 1 juv, 15.05.2012., leg. D. Antić; **AV05**: 2♂♂, 09.05.2018., leg. D. Antić; 1♀, 8 juv, 28.08.2018., leg. D. Antić; 1♀, 24.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; 1♀, leg. 12.07.2021., A. Marković; **AV07**: 1♀, 06.02.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, M. Šević; **AV16**: 1♀, 24.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić., S. Erčić; **AV18**: 2♀♀, 24.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV19**: 3♂♂, 1♀, 16.05.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić.

DISTRIBUTION: Bosnia & Herzegovina, Hungary, North Macedonia, Romania, Serbia (Kime and Enghoff 2011: 44).

CHOROTYPE: CSE.

Julida Brandt, 1833**Family Julidae Leach, 1814****10. *Cylindroiulus boleti* (C. L. Koch, 1847) Fig. 3A***Iulus boleti* C. L. Koch, 1847: 109.*Allajulus boleti* auct.*Diploiuulus boleti* auct.

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV02**: 1 juv, 21.11.2020., leg. D. Antić, D. Stojanović, A. Marković; **AV03**: 2♀♀, 21.11.2020., leg. D. Antić, D. Stojanović, A. Marković; **AV04**: 5 juv, 01.10.1995., leg. S. Makarov; 1 juv, 28.06.1995., leg. S. Makarov; 2♀♀, 13.04.1996., leg. S. Makarov; 1♀, 1 juv, 21.11.2020., leg. D. Antić, D. Stojanović, A. Marković; **AV05**: 1 juv, 12.07.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV07**: 1 juv, 06.02.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, M. Šević; **AV08**: 2 ♀♀, 06.02.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, M. Šević; **AV09**: 4♀♀, 4 juv, 14.03.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV10**: 2♂♂, 3♀♀, 3 juv, 14.03.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV11**: 4♂♂, 2♀♀, 4 juv, 14.03.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV12**: 3♂♂, 5♀♀, 14 juv, 27.03.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV13**: 1♂, 1♀, 2 juv, 06.02.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV14**: 4♂♂, 5♀♀, 6 juv, 10.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković, B. Stojanović; **AV15**: 2♂♂, 3♀♀, 7 juv, 10.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković, B. Sto-

Fig. 3. Representatives of Julida from Mt. Avala. **A**, *Cylindroiulus boleti* (C. L. Koch, 1847); **B**, *Megaphyllum bosniense* (Verhoeff, 1897); **C**, *Megaphyllum unilineatum* (C. L. Koch, 1938); **D**, *Pachyiulus hungaricus* (Karsch, 1881); **E**, *Unciger transsylvanicus* (Verhoeff, 1899). Photos by Dragan Antić.

janović; **AV16**: 4♀♀, 24.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV18**: 1♂, 3♀♀, 3 juv, 24.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV19**: 1 juv, 16.05.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV20**: 1♂, 2♀♀, 16.05.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV21**: 3♂♂, 3♀♀, 27.06.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV22**: 1♂, 2♀♀, 27.06.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV23**: 1 juv, 27.06.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić.

DISTRIBUTION: Albania, Austria, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Czech Republic, Croatia, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Moldova, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Ukraine (Kime and Enghoff 2017: 52).

CHOROTYPE: CES.

11. *Enantiulus nanus* (Latzel, 1884)

Iulus nanus Latzel, 1884: 264–267, figs 179–181.

Iulus albicornis Koch, 1847: 118, 119 [synonymized under *E. nanus* by Latzel (1884: 265)].

Iulus punctatus C. L. Koch, 1838: 22 [synonymized under *E. nanus* by Latzel (1884: 265)].

Iulus densestriatus Verhoeff, 1897c: 260 [synonymized under *E. nanus* by Schubart (1934: 230)].

Allaiulus nanus auct.

Allaiulus punctatus auct.

Leptophyllum nanum auct.

DISTRIBUTION: Austria, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Luxemburg, Montenegro, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Kime and Enghoff 2017: 90).

PUBLISHED DATA: Čarapićev Brest (**AV04**) (Makarov et al. 2003).

CHOROTYPE: EUR.

12. *Leptoiulus sarajevensis* Verhoeff, 1898

Iulus sarajevensis Verhoeff, 1898: 130, 131, figs 9, 10.

Macedoiulus storkani Verhoeff, 1932: 485–488, figs 15–17 [synonymized under *L. sarajevensis* by Mauriès et al. (1997: 291, 292)].

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV13**: 3♂♂, 5♀♀, 4 juv, 06.02.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV14**: 1♂, 7♀♀, 1 juv, 10.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković, B. Stojanović; **AV15**: 5♂♂, 4♀♀, 5 juv,

10.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković, B. Stojanović; **AV20**: 1♂, 7♀, 10 juv, 16.05.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV23**: 1♂, 10♀, 3 juv, 27.06.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić.

DISTRIBUTION: Bosnia & Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia (Kime and Enghoff 2017: 111).

PUBLISHED DATA: Without precise locality (Makarov et al. 2004).

CHOROTYPE: SEE.

13. *Leptoiulus trilineatus* (C. L. Koch, 1847)

Julus trilineatus C. L. Koch, 1847: 112.

Julus silvivaqus Verhoeff, 1898: 131 [synonymized under *L. trilineatus* by Attems (1927: 121)].

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV02**: 5♂♂, 4♀♀, 4 juv, 21.11.2020., leg. D. Antić, D. Stojanović, A. Marković; **AV04**: 1♂, 4♀♀, 3 juv, 1.7.1995., leg. S. Makarov; 1♂, 1♀, 2 juv, 21.11.2020., leg. D. Antić, D. Stojanović, A. Marković; **AV05**: 3♂♂, 1 juv, 21.11.2020., leg. D. Antić, D. Stojanović, A. Marković; 2♀♀, 24.04.2021., leg. A. Marković; **AV06**: 2♀♀, 06.02.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, M. Šević; **AV08**: 3♂♂, 2♀♀, 1 juv, 06.02.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, M. Šević; **AV09**: 1♂, 1♀, 14.03.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV12**: 1♂, 27.03.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV20**: 1♂, 1♀, 3 juv, 16.05.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić.

DISTRIBUTION: Albania, Austria, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Italy, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Romania, Serbia, Slovenia, Switzerland?, Turkey (Kime and Enghoff 2017: 114).

PUBLISHED DATA: Without precise locality (Tomić-Jovanović 1964; Boškova et al. 2000a).

CHOROTYPE: CSE.

14. *Megaphyllum bosniense* (Verhoeff, 1897) Fig. 3B

Brachyiulus bosniensis Verhoeff, 1897c: 110, figs 6, 7.

Chromatoiulus cotinophilus Loksa, 1962: 163, fig. 42, 43, [synonymized under *M. bosniense* by Lazányi and Vagalinski (2013: 78)].

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV02**: 2♂♂, 4♀♀, 3 juv, 21.11.2020., leg. D. Antić, D. Stojanović, A. Marković; **AV03**: 2♂♂, 8♀♀, 3 juv, 21.11.2020., leg. D. Antić, D. Stojanović, A. Marković; **AV04**: 3♀♀, 4 juv; 1.7.1995., leg. S. Makarov; 1♂, 21.11.2020., leg. D. Antić, D. Stojanović, A. Marković; **AV05**: 2♀♀, 25.4.2018.,

leg. D. Antić; 2♂♂, 5♀♀, 12.07.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV06**: 1♀, 1 juv, 06.02.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, M. Šević; **AV07**: 1♂, 1 juv, 06.02.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, M. Šević; **AV08**: 2♀♀, 06.02.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, M. Šević; **AV09**: 1♂, 14.03.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV11**: 1♀, 14.03.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV12**: 4♀♀, 27.03.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV13**: 1♂, 2♀♀, 06.02.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV14**: 2♀♀, 10.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković, B. Stojanović; **AV15**: 2♀♀, 3 juv, 10.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković, B. Stojanović; **AV18**: 1♀, 2 juv, 24.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV19**: 2♂♂, 2♀♀, 1 juv, 16.05.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV20**: 1♂, 4♀♀, 4 juv, 16.05.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV21**: 2♂♂, 5♀♀, 3 juv, 27.06.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV22**: 1♀, 2 juv, 27.06.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić.

DISTRIBUTION: Albania, Austria, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Hungary, Italia, North Macedonia, Montenegro, Romania, Serbia, Slovenia (Kime and Enghoff 2017: 119).

PUBLISHED DATA: Čarapićev Brest (**AV04**) (Vujić et al. 2018; Ilić et al. 2019).

CHOROTYPE: CSE.

15. *Megaphyllum unilineatum* (C. L. Koch, 1938) Fig. 3C

Julus unilineatus C. L. Koch, 1838: 9, fig. 9.

Julus gilvolineatus L. Koch, 1881: 674 [synonymized under *M. unilineatus* by Enghoff and Vicente (2000: 196)].

Julus balearicus L. Koch, 1881: 675 [synonymized under *M. unilineatus* by Enghoff and Vicente (2000: 196)].

Iulus frivaldszkyi Daday, 1889: 54 [synonymized under *I. unilineatus* by Attems (1895: 208)].

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV08**: 1♀, 06.02.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, M. Šević.

DISTRIBUTION: Albania, Austria, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia (Kime and Enghoff 2017: 130).

PUBLISHED DATA: Without precise locality (Boškova et al. 2000a).

CHOROTYPE: CSE.

16. *Pachyiulus hungaricus* (Karsch, 1881) Fig. 3D

Julus hungaricus Karsch, 1881: 17, 18.

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV04**: 1♂, 3♀♀, 1 juv, 28.06.1995., leg. S. Makarov; 1♂, 4.3.2021., leg. D. Antić, M. Šević; **AV07**: 1♂, 6♀♀, 06.02.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, M. Šević; **AV11**: 1 juv, 14.03.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV14**: 2 juv, 10.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković, B. Stojanović; **AV21**: 1 juv, 27.06.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV23**: 2 juv, 27.06.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić.

DISTRIBUTION: Albania, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Romania, Serbia (Kime and Enghoff 2017: 152).

PUBLISHED DATA: Čarapićev Brest (**AV04**) (Ilić et al. 2019); without precise locality (Tomić-Jovanović 1964; Boškova et al. 2000; Santamaria et al. 2016; Stanković et al. 2016)

CHOROTYPE: SEE.

17. *Unciger transsylvanicus* (Verhoeff, 1899) Fig. 3E

Leptophyllum transsylvanicum Verhoeff, 1899: 187, 188, figs 12–14.

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV04**: 1♀, 21.11.2020., leg. D. Antić, D. Stojanović, A. Marković; **AV21**: 1♂, 1 juv, 27.06.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **Without precise locality**: 4♂♂, 8♀♀, 6 juv, 17.4.1997., leg. S. Makarov.

DISTRIBUTION: Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Ukraine (Kime and Enghoff 2017: 169).

PUBLISHED DATA: Without precise locality (Makarov et al. 2004).

CHOROTYPE: CES.

REMARKS: *Unciger foetidus* (C. L. Koch, 1838) was also mentioned on Mt. Avala (Boškova et al. 2000a), but examination of IZB collections and fresh samples yielded only *U. transsylvanicus* (see under Discussion).

Polydesmida Pocock, 1887

Family Paradoxosomatidae Daday, 1889

18. *Strongylosoma stigmatosum* (Eichwald, 1830) Fig. 4A

Julus stigmatosus Eichwald, 1830: 124.

Iulus pallipes Olivier, 1792: 416 [synonymized under *Strongylosoma stigmatosum* by Jeekel (1968: 38)].

Strongylosoma iuloides Brandt, 1833: 205 [synonymized under *Strongylosoma*

Fig. 4. Representatives of Polydesmida from Mt. Avala. **A**, *Strongylosoma stigmatosum* (Eichwald, 1830); **B**, *Brachydesmus dadayi* Verhoeff, 1895; **C**, *Brachydesmus polydesmoides* Verhoeff, 1895; **D**, *Polydesmus collaris* C.L. Koch, 1847; **E**, *Polydesmus complanatus* (Linnaeus, 1761). Photos by Dragan Antić.

stigmatosum by Jeekel (1968: 39)].

Strongylosoma corrugatum (Koch, 1847): 129 [synonymized under *Strongylosoma pallipes* by Latzel (1884: 168)].

Strongylosoma ferrugineum (Koch, 1847): 130 [synonymized under *Strongylosoma pallipes* by Latzel (1884: 168)].

Strongylosoma vejdoskyi Němec, 1895: 1–6, figs 1–8 [synonymized under *Strongylosoma stigmatosum* by Schubart (1934: 173)].

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV20**: 1♂, 3 juv, 16.05.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić.
 DISTRIBUTION: Albania, Austria, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Belarus, Croatia, Czech Republic, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Ukraine (Kime and Enghoff 2011: 54).
 CHOROTYPE: CES.

Family **Polydesmidae Leach, 1816**

19. *Brachydesmus avalae* Ćurčić and Makarov, 1997

Brachydesmus avalae Ćurčić and Makarov, 1997: 33, figs 1–6.

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV15**: 1♂, 10.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković, B. Stojanović; **AV19**: 5♂♂, 5♀♀, 5 juv, 16.05.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić.

DISTRIBUTION: Serbia – Endemic species (Kime and Enghoff 2011: 55).

PUBLISHED DATA: Without precise locality (Ćurčić and Makarov 1997; Makarov et al. 2004).

CHOROTYPE: SEE.

REMARKS: See under *B. polydesmoides* Verhoeff, 1895.

20. *Brachydesmus dadayi* Verhoeff, 1895 Fig. 4B

Brachydesmus dadayi Verhoeff, 1895b: 286, 287, fig. 4.

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV01**: 1♂, 21.11.2020, leg. D. Antić, D. Stojanović, A. Marković; **AV04**: 1♀, 27.04.1992.; 2♂♂, 1♀, 21.11.2020., leg. D. Antić, D. Stojanović, A. Marković; **AV05**: 1♂, 4♀♀, 24.4.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić., S. Erčić; 1♀, 12.07.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV08**: 3♂♂, 7♀♀, 06.02.2021, leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, M. Šević; **AV11**: 1♂, 14.03.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV12**: 4♂♂, 7♀♀, leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV13**: 2♂♂, 3.3.2019., leg D. Antić and D. Stojanović; 3♂♂, 4♀♀, leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV14**: 1♂, 1 juv, 10.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković, B. Stojanović; **AV17**: 4♀♀, 1 juv, 24.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković, B. Stojanović; **AV18**: 1♂, 1♀, 2 juv, 24.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV20**: 1 juv, 16.05.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **“Without precise locality”**: 1 ♂, 11.03.2018., leg. D. Antić.

DISTRIBUTION: Bulgaria, Hungary, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia (Kime and Enghoff 2011: 55).

PUBLISHED DATA: Without precise locality (Ćurčić and Makarov 1996; Makarov et

al. 2004).

CHOROTYPE: CSE.

21. *Brachydesmus polydesmoides* Verhoeff, 1895 Fig. 4C

Brachydesmus polydesmoides Verhoeff, 1895b: 3, fig. 2.

Brachydesmus calcivagus Verhoeff, 1898b: 371, figs 15, 16 [synonymized under *B. polydesmoides* by Strasser (1969: 143)].

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV04**: 2♂♂, 1♀, 12.11.2013., leg. D. Antić; **AV09**: 2♂♂, 5♀♀, 1 juv, 14.03.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV10**: 1♂, 1 juv, 14.03.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV13**: 1♂, 3♀♀, 06.02.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV16**: 6♂♂, 7♀♀, 6 juv, 24.04.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić.

DISTRIBUTION: Bosnia & Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Montenegro, Romania, Serbia (Kime and Enghoff 2011: 58).

CHOROTYPE: SEE.

REMARKS: Mršić (1985: 150, 151, fig. 3) illustrated quite a diverse range of gonopod variations in *Brachydesmus polydesmoides*. *Brachydesmus avalae* has an identical “polydesmoid” habitus as *B. polydesmoides*, moreover individuals of both species can be found in syntopy. Based on this and the structure of the gonopods of *B. avalae*, which fits into the range of gonopod variation of *B. polydesmoides*, it seems possible that *B. avalae* is a junior subjective synonym of *B. polydesmoides*. Further comparative analysis of different populations from different localities is necessary to clarify the situation.

22. *Polydesmus collaris* C. L. Koch, 1847 Fig. 4D

Polydesmus (Spanobranchyum) collaris C. L. Koch, 1847: 133.

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV04**: 2♀♀, 04.03.2021., leg. D. Antić, M. Šević.

DISTRIBUTION: Albania, Austria, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Italy, Hungary, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Romania, Serbia, Slovenia (Kime and Enghoff 2011: 62).

PUBLISHED DATA: Without precise locality (Mršić 1988; Vučković 1956).

CHOROTYPE: CSE.

REMARKS: *Polydesmus collaris* is a large and readily distinguishable species, very often seen at the locality **AV04**, but we collected only two specimens for this study.

23. *Polydesmus complanatus* (Linnaeus, 1761) Fig. 4E

Iulus complanatus Linnaeus, 1761: 502.

Polydesmus illyricus Verhoeff, 1893: 273–275, fig. 1 [synonymized under *P. complanatus* by Lohmander (1925: 16, 17)].

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV04**: 1♂, 1 juv, 21.11.2020., leg. D. Antić, D. Stojanović, A. Marković; **AV09**: 2♀♀, 14.03.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV10**: 2♀♀, 14.03.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV13**: 1♂, 06.02.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić, S. Erčić, J. Novaković; **AV21**: 1♂, 1 juv, 27.06.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić.

DISTRIBUTION: Albania, Austria, Belarus, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Croatia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine (Kime and Enghoff 2011: 62).

CHOROTYPE: CSE.

24. *Polydesmus ingoratus* Ceuca 1964

Polydesmus ingoratus Ceuca 1964: 39–41, fig. 1.

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV21**: 1♂, 27.06.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić; **AV23**: 2♂♂, 1 juv, 27.06.2021., leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić.

DISTRIBUTION: Montenegro, Serbia (Kime and Enghoff 2011: 64).

CHOROTYPE: DIN.

25. *Polydesmus schaessburgensis* Verhoeff, 1898

Polydesmus schaessburgensis Verhoeff, 1898b: 365, figs 1–3.

MATERIAL EXAMINED: **AV16**: 8♂♂, 1♀, 7 juv, leg. A. Marković, M. Grujić., S. Erčić.

DISTRIBUTION: Hungary, Moldova, Romania, Serbia, Ukraine (Kime and Enghoff 2011: 67).

PUBLISHED DATA: Čarapićev Brest (**AV04**) (Makarov et al. 2004).

CHOROTYPE: CEE.

DISCUSSION

In this study, we have listed 25 species of millipedes belonging to 18 genera and 11 families within seven orders. The family with the greatest number of species is Julidae with eight species, followed by Polydesmidae and Glomeridae with seven and two species, respectively. The remaining eight families, viz., Polyxenidae, Polyzoni-

idae, Chordeumatidae, Mastigophorophyllidae, Craspedosomatidae, Verhoeffiidae, Dorypetalidae and Paradoxosomatidae are each represented by a single species.

The species *Haplogona oculodistincta* (Verhoeff, 1893) and the family Verhoeffiidae, to which it belongs, are both newly recorded in the Serbian fauna. Furthermore, we exclude four species that were previously listed as present on Mt. Avala because they were misidentified or most probably misidentified. The species excluded from the list are *Polyxenus lagurus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Julus terrestris* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Pachyiulus cattarensis* (Latzel, 1884) and *Unciger foetidus* (C.L. Koch, 1838). There was a misidentification involving confusion of *Propolyxenus argentifer* (Verhoeff, 1921) with *Polyxenus lagurus*. Upon examining of material collected during the field studies, and material from the IZB collection [(identified as *P. lagurus* and published in Makarov et al. (2004)], all specimens belong to *Propolyxenus argentifer*. The first findings of *P. argentifer* from Serbia were only recently published, from Belgrade (Short et al. 2020). *Unciger foetidus* was also mentioned for Mt. Avala (Boškova et al. 2000a), but after reviewing material from both field surveys and the IZB collection we believe that *U. transsylvanicus* (Verhoeff, 1899) is, in fact, the sole species of the genus *Unciger* Brandt, 1841 on Mt. Avala. *Unciger foetidus* mainly inhabits Central Europe, while in the south, towards the Balkans, *Unciger transsylvanicus* becomes a more dominant species; although we emphasize that the ranges of the two species overlap (Kime and Enghoff 2017).

We also note that previous findings for two other species on Mt. Avala, viz., *Julus terrestris* and *Pachyiulus cattarensis*, are questionable, and we rather believe they do not inhabit this mountain. Both species are listed for Mt. Avala in papers by Vučković (1956) and Boškova et al. (2000). Vučković (1956) mentioned *Julus terrestris* as *J. fallax* Meinert, 1868, now a synonym for *Ophiyulus pilosus* (Newport, 1843), but neither species was found during field surveys. As already stated, *J. terrestris* prefers lowland riparian forests and marshes, and Mt. Avala does not support any of such habitats. Regarding *P. cattarensis*, based on the range and habitat preferences of this species, as well as its general distribution, it can be asserted that this was an odd finding, as the species prefers warm and somewhat dry rocky habitats from the southern and eastern parts of Serbia.

Zoogeographically, the millipede fauna of Mt. Avala shows prevalent Central-Southeast European and Central-East-Southeast European chorotypes (Fig. 5). It is of interest to note that Mt. Avala is inhabited by a few endemic or subendemic species. For example, *B. avalae* is a stenoendemic, *P. ignoratus* and *L. sarajevensis* are Balkan endemics, while *P. hungaricus* and *B. polydesmoides* belong to the category of Balkan subendemics. It is well-known that natural habitats throughout the world are being disturbed and destroyed at alarming rates, which results in a massive loss of species. Thus, it is not completely excluded that some of the taxa that we deleted from the list really once lived

Fig. 5. Zoogeographical characteristics of diplopod fauna of Mt. Avala. The abbreviations used for zoogeographical categories: CEE – Central East European; CES – Central-East-Southeast European; CSE– Central-Southeast European; DIN – Dinaric; EUR – European; SEE– Southeast European; TEM: Turano–Eastern Mediterranean. Numbers indicate a count of species belonging to a particular chorotype (X-axis).

on or in the vicinity of Mt. Avala, or still inhabiting some small remnant of the former habitat. Knowledge of species numbers on both the local and the global levels is important for providing a reference point from which to estimate biodiversity loss. The creation of legislative instruments has been an important factor in the preservation of biological diversity. One example is the area studied. To be specific, Mt. Avala was without legal protection prior to 2007. After that, it became a protected natural area of local importance (protection category III). Such a decision has been crucial in the preservation of diplopods and other soil arthropods in this area. Although Mt. Avala is in the immediate vicinity of the city of Belgrade and under great negative anthropogenic pressure, 25 confirmed species of millipedes - representing almost a fourth of the known diplopods on the territory of Serbia - have been preserved in such a relatively small area. We think that the creation of micro-reserves and a change of the protection category should be considered in order to protect such especially sensitive terrestrial organisms.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We are grateful to all colleagues who helped us with collecting millipedes on Mt. Avala. Our gratitude goes to Hans Reip (Jena, Germany) for his comments and corrections that improved this manuscript. This study was partly supported by the Serbian Ministry of Science, Technological development and innovation (grant no. 51-03-47/2023-01/200178).

REFERENCES

- ANTIĆ DŽ, ČURČIĆ BPM, TOMIĆ VT, ČURČIĆ SB, STOJANOVIĆ DZ, DUDIĆ BD, MAKAROV SE. 2013. One hundred millipede species in Serbia (Arthropoda: Myriapoda: Diplopoda). *Archives of Biological Sciences*. 65(4):1559–1578.
- ANTIĆ DŽ, ŠEVIĆ M, MACEK O, AKKARI N. 2021. Review of *Trachysphaera* Heller, 1858 (Diplopoda: Glomerida: Glomeridae) in Serbia, with taxonomic notes on the genus. *Zootaxa*. 5047(3):273–299.
- ATTEMS C. 1895. Die Myriopoden Steiermarks. *Sitzungsberichte, Akademie der Wissenschaften in Wien, Mathematisch-Naturwissenschaftliche Klasse, Abteilung I*. 104:117–238.
- ATTEMS C. 1902. Myriopoden von Kreta nebst Beiträgen zur allgemeinen Kenntnis einiger Gattungen. *Sitzungsberichte, Akademie der Wissenschaften in Wien, Mathematisch-Naturwissenschaftliche Klasse, Abteilung I*. 111:527–614.
- ATTEMS C. 1927. Über palaearktische Diplopoden. R. Stricker. *Archiv für Naturgeschichte*. 1. Heft:145–256.
- ATTEMS C. 1929. Die Myriapoden fauna von Albanien und Jugoslawien. *Zoologische Jahrbücher (Systematik)*. 56(3/4):173–356.
- ATTEMS C. 1959. Die Myriapoden der Höhlen der Balkanhalbinsel. Nachdem Material der „Biospeleologica Balcanica“. *Annalen des Naturhistorischen Museums in Wien, Wien*. 63:281–406.
- BORISAVLJEVIĆ Lj, JOVANOVIĆ-DUNJIĆ R, MIŠIĆ V. 1955. Vegetacija Avale. *Zbornik radova Instituta za ekologiju i biogeografiju Srpske Akademije Nauka*. 6(3):3–43.
- BOŠKOVA T, NIKOLIĆ G, MAKAROV SE, TOMIĆ VT, ROMAC S, ČURČIĆ BPM. 2000. Protein electrophoresis patterns of body extracts and generic identification of some diplopods (Myriapoda). *Archives of Biological Sciences, Belgrade*. 52:23–24.
- BOŠKOVA T, NIKOLIĆ G, MAKAROV SE, ROMAC S, ČURČIĆ BPM. 2000a. Identification of some diplopod taxa by electrophoresis (Diplopoda: Myriapoda). *Archives of Biological Sciences, Belgrade*. 52:31–32.

- BRAGIN NY, BRAGINA LG, DJERIĆ N, TOLJIĆ M. 2011. Triassic and Jurassic radiolarians from sedimentary blocks of ophiolite mélangé in the Avala Gora area (Belgrade surroundings, Serbia). *Stratigraphy and Geological Correlation*. 19(6):631–640.
- BRANDT JF. 1833. Tentaminum quorundam monographicorum Insecta Myriapoda Chilognathi Latreillii spectantium prodromus. *Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou*. 6:194–209.
- BROLEMANN HW. 1895. Genre *Latzelia*. *Zoologischer Anzeiger*. 18(490):458–459.
- BROLEMANN HW. 1935. Myriapodes Diplopodes (Chilognathes I). *Faune de France*. 29:1–369.
- CEUCA T. 1964. Zur Kenntnis der Höhlendiplopoden Jugoslawiens. *Prirodnaučen muzej*. Skopje. 5:37–46.
- COOK OF, COLLINS GN. 1895. The Craspedosomatidae of North America. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*. 9:1–100.
- ĆURČIĆ BPM, MAKAROV SE. 1996. Postembryonic development of *Brachydesmus dadayii* (Polydesmidae, Diplopoda), from Yugoslavia. 1st Congress of Biologist of Macedonia, Ohrid, Abstracts. 1:14.
- ĆURČIĆ BPM, MAKAROV SE. 1997. Diversification and biogeographic features of millipedes in Serbia, Yugoslavia. *Entomologica Scandinavica, Supplementum*, Lund. 51:191–197.
- ĆURČIĆ BPM, MAKAROV SE. 1997a. *Brachydesmus (Stylobrachydesmus) avalae*, a new endemic millipede (Diplopoda, Polydesmidae) from Serbia (Yugoslavia). *Archives of Biological Sciences, Belgrade*. 49:33–34.
- ĆURČIĆ BPM, MAKAROV SE. 1998. New report on soil-dwelling millipedes (Diplopoda, Myriapoda) from West Serbia. *Archives of Biological Sciences, Belgrade*. 50:5–6.
- EICHWALD DE. 1830. *Expositio animalibus tum vivis, tum fossilibus potissimum Rossiae in universum, et Poloniae in specie. Pars altera*. Vilnae: J. Zawadzki. 1829–1831
- ENGHOFF H, VICENTE MC. 2000. Millipedes of the Balearic Islands, and the identity of the species described by L. Koch in 1881 (Diplopoda). *Steenstrupia*. 25(2):195–200.
- ENGHOFF H, GOLOVATCH SI, SHORT M, STOEV P, WESENER T. 2015. Diplopoda—Taxonomic overview. In: Minelli, A. (Ed.) *Treatise on zoology—anatomy, taxonomy, biology. The Myriapoda*. Volume 2. Brill, Leiden. p. 363–454.
- FODDAI D, MINELLI A, SCHELLER U, ZAPPAROLI M. 1995. Chilopoda, Diplopoda, Pauropoda, Symphyla. In A Minelli, S Ruffo, S La Posta, *Checklist delle Specie della Fauna d'Italia*. 9(32):1–35.

- GOLOVATCH SI, HOFFMAN RL. 2000. On the diplopod taxa and type material of J. F. Brandt, with some new descriptions and identities (Diplopoda). *Fragmenta faunistica*, Supplement. 43:229–249.
- HAASE E. (1886). Schlesiens Diplopeden. *Zeitschrift für Entomologie*. 11:8–64.
- HAUSER H. 2001. Untersuchungen zur Systematik, Biogeographie und Evolution von *Craspedosoma rawlinsii* Leach, 1815 (Diplopoda, Chordeumatida). Dissertation. Fachbereich Biologie, Geo- und Umweltwissenschaften, Universität Oldenburg. Götting. 77pp.
- HAUSER H. 2004. Untersuchungen zur Systematik und Biogeografie der *Craspedosoma rawlinsii* Leach-Gruppe (Diplopoda: Chordeumatida: Craspedosomatidae). *Entomologische Nachrichten und Berichte c/o B. Klausnitzer*. 9:1–32.
- HAUSER H. 2004a. Zur Taxonomie und Systematik von *Mastigona bosniensis* (Verhoeff, 1897) und *Mastigona vihorlatica* (Attems, 1899) (Diplopoda, Chordeumatida, Mastigophorophyllidae). *Entomologische Nachrichten und Berichte* 48:215–218.
- HELLER C. 1858. Beiträge zur österreichischen Grotten-Fauna. Sitzungsberichte der Mathematisch-Naturwissenschaftlichen Classe der Kaiserlichen Akademie der Wissenschaften, Wien. 26(1):313–326.
- ILIĆ BS, VUJIĆ VD, JOVANOVIĆ ZS, PAVKOVIĆ-LUČIĆ SB, DUDIĆ BD, LUČIĆ LR, MAKAROV SE. 2019. Sexual dimorphism in some morphological traits of three European millipedes (Diplopoda, Julida, Julidae). *Animal Biology*. 69(4):483–496.
- JEEKELE CAW. 1968. *Julus pallipes* Olivier, 1792. (Diplopoda, Polydesmida): Proposed Suppression under the plenary powers. *Z.N. (S.) 1823 Bulletin of Zoological Nomenclature*. 25(1):38–40.
- KIME RD, ENGHOFF H. 2011. Atlas of European Millipedes (Class Diplopoda). Volume 1. Orders Polyxenida, Glomerida, Platydesmida, Siphonocryptida, Polyzoniida, Callipodida, Polydesmida. Co-published by Pensoft Publishers, Sofia–Moscow and European Invertebrate Survey, Leiden. 1–282.
- KIME RD, ENGHOFF H. 2017. Atlas of European millipedes 2: Order Julida (Class Diplopoda). *European Journal of Taxonomy*. 346:1–299.
- KIME RD, ENGHOFF H. 2021. Atlas of European millipedes 3: Order Chordeumatida (Class Diplopoda). *European Journal of Taxonomy*. 769:1–244.
- KOCH CL. 1838. Deutschlands Crustaceen. Myriapoden und Arachniden [Crustaceans of Germany. Myriapods and Spiders] – In: Panzer; Herrich-Schäffer A. (ed.). Deutschlands Insecten. Heft 22:1–16.
- KOCH CL. 1847. System der Myriapoden mit den Verzeichnissen und Berichtigungen zu Deutschlands Crustaceen, Myriapoden und Arachniden. In: Panzer

- G.W.F. and Herrich-Schäffer A. (eds) Kritische Revision der Insectenfauna Deutschlands. III:1–196.
- KOCH CL. 1881. Zoologische Ergebnisse von Excursionen auf den Balearen. II. Arachniden und Myriapoden [Zoological results of excursions in the Balearic Islands. II. Arachnids and Myriapods]. Verhandlungen der Zoologisch-botanischen Gesellschaft in Wien. 31:625–678.
- KORSÓS Z. 1994. Checklist, preliminary distribution maps, and bibliography of millipedes in Hungary (Diplopoda). *Miscellanea zoologica hungarica*. 9:29–82.
- LATZEL R. 1882. Beitrag zur Myriapoden Kenntnis Österreich-Ungarns und Serbiens. Verhandlungen des Zoologisch-Botanischen Vereins in Wien. 32:281–282.
- LATZEL R. 1884. Die Myriapoden der Osterreichischen-Ungarischen Monarchie. Zweite Hälfte, Wien. 1:1–414.
- LAZÁNYI E, VAGALINSKI B. 2013. Redefinition of the millipede subgenus *Megaphyllum* sensu stricto Verhoeff, 1894 and neotype designation for *Megaphyllum austriacum* (Latzel, 1884) (Myriapoda: Diplopoda: Julida: Julidae). *Zootaxa*. 3741(1):55–100.
- LEACH WE. 1814. A tabular view of the external characters of four classes of animals. The transactions of the Linnean society of London. 11(2):306–400.
- LIGNAU N. 1903. Die Myriopoden am kaukasischen Schwarzmeererfer. Mémoires de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de la Nouvelle-Russie. 25(1):82–149
- LINNAEUS C. 1758. *Systema Naturae per regna tria naturae, secundum classes, ordines, genera, species, cum characteribus, differentiis, synonymis, locis*. Editio decima, reformata [10th revised edition], vol. 1: 824 pp. Laurentius Salvius: Stockholm
- LINNAEUS C. 1761. *Fauna Svecica* [Fauna of Sweden]. Ed. Ima, Stockholm. 1746.
- LOKSA I. 1962. Einige neue und wenig bekannte Diplopoden aus Ungarn. *Annales Universitatis Scientiarum Budapestinensis de Rolando Eötvös nominatae, sectio Biologica*. 5:157–170.
- MEINERT FVA. 1868. Danmarks chilognather. *Naturhistorisk Tidskrift*, 3. Raekke, 5:1–32.
- MAKAROV SE, MITIĆ BM, ČURČIĆ SB. 2002. On two new cave diplopods from Serbia (Diplopoda: Julida). *Israel Journal of Zoology*. 48:235–242.
- MAKAROV SE, MITIĆ BM, TOMIĆ VT. 2003. On the evolutionary status of *Enantiulus nanus acutus* (Attems, 1929) (Julidae, Diplopoda). *Archives of Biological Sciences, Belgrade*. 55(1–2):15–16.
- MAKAROV SE, MITIĆ BM, ČURČIĆ SB. 2003. *Svarogosoma bozidarcurcici* n. g., n. sp. (Diplopoda, Anthroleucosomatidae) from Balkan Peninsula, with notes on

- its phylogeny. *Periodicum Biologorum*. 105(4):465–472.
- MAKAROV SE, MITIĆ BM, TOMIĆ VT, ČURČIĆ, BPM. 2003. The millipedes (Diplopoda, Myriapoda) of Mt. Kopaonik. *Archives of Biological Sciences, Belgrade*. 56(3–4):97–101.
- MAKAROV SE, ČURČIĆ BPM, TOMIĆ VT, LEGAKIS A. 2004. The Diplopods of Serbia, Montenegro, and the Republic of Macedonia. Belgrade, Athens: Institute of Zoology, Faculty of Biology, University of Belgrade; Hellenic Zoological Society; Committee for Karst and Speleology, Serbian Academy of Science and Arts.
- MAURIÈS JP, GOLOVATCH SI, STOEV PE. 1997. The millipedes of Albania: recent data, new taxa; systematical, nomenclatural and faunistical review (Myriapoda, Diplopoda). *Zoosystema*. 19(2–3):255–292.
- MCALPINE DF, SHEAR W. 2018. The millipede *Craspedosoma raulinsii* Leach, 1814 (Chordeumatida: Craspedosomatidae) in North America with comments on the derivation of its binomial name. *Zootaxa*. 4455(2):389–394.
- MRŠIĆ N. 1985. Contribution to the Knowledge of Diplopods (Myriapoda: Diplopoda) of Serbia. *Bulletin of Natural History Museum, Belgrade*. 40 (B):143–168.
- MRŠIĆ N. 1988. Polydesmida (Diplopoda) of Yugoslavia. 1. *Rasprave IV. Razreda SAZU*. 29:69–112.
- NĚMEC B. 1896. O novém Diplopodu z rodu *Strongylosoma*. *Vestník Královské České Společnosti Nauk, Třída Mathematicko-Prírodovedecká*. 1895:1–6.
- OLIVIER GA. 1792. *Insectes Enciclopedie methodique* (Vol. 7). Paris. 827
- PORAT, CO. 1889. Nya bidrag till skandinaviska halföns myriopodologi. *Germandts*. 113–148
- RUNDIĆ L, KNEŽEVIĆ S. 2017. The Miocene fossiliferous sites of the Avala Mt. (Belgrade area, Serbia) and their importance. *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum*. 10:29–41.
- RUNDIĆ Lj, GANIĆ M, KNEŽEVIĆ S, RADIVOJEVIĆ D, RADONJIĆ M. 2019. Stratigraphic implications of the Mio-Pliocene geodynamics in the area of Mt. Avala: new evidence from Torlak Hill and Beli Potok (Belgrade, Serbia). *Geologia Croatica*. 72:109–128.
- SABOLJEVIĆ MS, CVETIĆ T. 2003. Bryophyte flora of Avala Mt. (C. Serbia, Yugoslavia) *Lindbergia Lund*. 28:90–96.
- SANTAMARIA S, ENGHOFF H, REBOLEIRA AS. 2016. Hidden biodiversity revealed by collections-based research-Laboulbeniales in millipedes: genus *Rickia*. *Phytotaxa*. 243(2):101–127.
- SCHUBART O. 1934. Tausendfüßler oder Myriapoda. I: Diplopoda. *Die Tierwelt*

- Deutschlands und der angrenzenden Meeresteile. Jena. 28:1–318.
- SCHUBART O. 1964. Diplopoda, Symphyla, Pauropoda, Chilopoda (Ergänzung). Ed. Brohmer P, Ehrmann P, Ulmer G. Die Tierwelt Mitteleuropas. II. Band. 3:1–55.
- SHORT M, VAHTERA V, WESENER T, GOLOVATCH SI. 2020. The millipede family Polyxenidae (Diplopoda, Polyxenida) in the faunas of the Crimean Peninsula and the Caucasus, with notes on other European Polyxenidae. Zootaxa. 4772(2):306–332
- SHELLEY RM. 1997. The millipede family Polyzoniidae in North America, with a classification of the global fauna (Diplopoda, Polyzoniida). Arthropoda Selecta. 6(3/4):3–34.
- SILLABER H. 1987. Zur *Trachysphaera schmidtii* in Kärnten (Myriapoda, Diplopoda). Carinthia, II, Klagenfurt. 177(97):179–188.
- SPELDA J. 1991. Zur Faunistik und Systematik der Tausendfüßler (Myriapoda) Südwestdeutschlands. Jahreshefte der Gesellschaft für Naturkunde in Württemberg. 146:211–232.
- STANKOVIĆ S, DIMKIĆ I, VUJISIĆ L, PAVKOVIĆ-LUČIĆ S, JOVANOVIĆ Z, STEVIĆ T, TOMIĆ V. 2016. Chemical defence in a millipede: Evaluation and characterization of antimicrobial activity of the defensive secretion from *Pachyiulus hungaricus* (Karsch, 1881) (Diplopoda, Julida, Julidae). PLoS One. 11(12):e0167249.
- STOEV P, ENGHOFF H. 2006. A review of the millipede genus *Dorypetalum* Verhoeff, 1900 (Diplopoda: Callipodida: Dorypetalidae). Zootaxa. 1254(1):29–43.
- STRASSER K. 1969. Über Diplopoden Bulgariens, II [On the Diplopods of Bulgaria, II]. Annales zoologici: 27(7):133–168.
- STRASSER K. 1971. Diplopoda, Catalogues Faunae Jugoslaviae. Consilium Academicarum Scientiarum Rei Publicae Socialisticae Foederativae Jugoslaviae, Academia Scientiarum et Artium Slovenica. III/5:1–50.
- STRASSER K. 1976. Über Diplopoda-Chilognata Griechenlands, II [On diplopods of Greece II]. Revue suisse de Zoologie. 83(3):579–645.
- ŠEVIĆ M, STOJANOVIĆ D, STANKOVIĆ M, ŠČIBAN M, ANTIĆ, D. 2022. Fauna Diplopoda (Arthropoda: Myriapoda) specijalnog rezervata prirode „Zasavica”. In: Simić, S. (Ed.), Naučno-stručni skup o biodiverzitetu i drugim vrednostima rezervata Zasavica „ZASAVICA 2022“, Zasavica, 25. novembar 2022, Zbornik radova, 123–132. Sremska Mitrovica: Pokret Gorana.
- TAJOVSKÝ K. 2001. Millipedes (Diplopoda) of the Czech Republic. Myriapodologica Czecho-Slovaca. 1:11–24.
- TAGLIANTI AV, AUDISIO PA, BIONDI M, BOLOGNA MA, CARPANETO GM, DE BLASE A, FATTORINI S, PIATTELLA E, SINDACO R, VENCHI A, ZAPPAROLI M. 1999. A pro-

- posal for a chorotype classification of the Near East fauna, in the framework of the Western Palearctic region. *Biogeographia*. 20(1):32–59.
- TOMIĆ–JOVANOVIĆ V. 1964. Prilog poznavanju Myriapoda Jugoslavije. *Bulletin du Museum d’Historienaturelle*, Belgrade. 19:189–194.
- VERHOEFF KW. 1891. Ein Beitrag zur mitteleuropäischen Diplopodenfauna. *Berliner entomologische Zeitschrift*. 36(1):115–166.
- VERHOEFF KW. 1893. Neue Diplopoden aus dem österreichischen Küstenlande. *Berliner entomologische Zeitschrift*. 38(3):267–278 .
- VERHOEFF KW. 1895a. Aphorismen zur Biologie, Morphologie, Gattungs- und Art-Systematik der Diplopoden. *Zoologischer Anzeiger*. 18(476–478):203–244.
- VERHOEFF KW. 1895b. Beiträge zur Kenntnis paläarktischer Myriopoden. I. Aufsatz: Über einige neue Myriopoden der österreichisch-ungarischen Monarchie. *Verhandlungen der Zoologisch–botanischen Gesellschaft in Wien*. 45:284–298.
- VERHOEFF KW. 1897. Beiträge zur Kenntnis paläarktischer Myriopoden V. Aufsatz: Übersicht der mir genauer bekannten europäischen Chordeumiden-Gattungen. *Archiv für Naturgeschichte*. 63(1):129–138.
- VERHOEFF KW. 1897a. Über Diplopoden aus Bosnien, Herzegowina und Dalmatien II. Theil: Chordeumidae und Lysiopetalidae. *Archiv für Naturgeschichte*. 63(1):147–156.
- VERHOEFF KW. 1897b. Über Diplopoden aus Bosnien, Herzegowina und Dalmatien III. Theil: Chordeumidae und Lysiopetalidae (Fortsetzung). *Archiv für Naturgeschichte*. 63(1):181–204.
- VERHOEFF KW. 1897c. Beiträge zur vergleichenden Morphologie, Gattungs- und Artsystematik der Diplopoden, mit besonderer Berücksichtigung derjenigen Siebenbürgens. *Zoologischer Anzeiger*. 20(528):97–125.
- VERHOEFF KW. 1898. Über Diplopoden aus Bosnien, Herzegowina und Dalmatien IV. Theil: Julidae; V. Enthaltend: Schlüssel und Stammbaum von *Leptoiulus*, sowie einige andere europäische Juliden. *Archiv für Naturgeschichte*. 64(1):119–160.
- VERHOEFF KW. 1898a. Über Diplopoden aus Bosnien, Herzegowina und Dalmatien. V. Theil: Glomeridae und Polyzooniidae (Schluss). *Archiv für Naturgeschichte*. 64(1):161–176.
- VERHOEFF KW. 1898b. Beiträge zur Kenntnis paläarktischer Myriopoden. VII. Aufsatz: Ueber neue und wenig bekannte Polydesmiden aus Siebenbürgen, Rumänien und dem Banat. *Archiv für Naturgeschichte*. 64(1):363–372.
- VERHOEFF KW. 1899. Beiträge zur Kenntniss paläarktischer Myriopoden. IX. Aufsatz: Zur Systematik, Phylogenie und vergleichenden Morphologie der Juliden und über einige andere Diplopoden. *Archiv für Naturgeschichte*. 65(1):183–

220.

- VERHOEFF KW. 1901. Beiträge zur Kenntniss paläarktischer Myriopoden. XX. Aufsatz: Diplopoden des östlichen Mittelmeergebietes. Archiv für Naturgeschichte. 67(1):241–270.
- VERHOEFF KW. 1906. Über Diplopoden. 5. (25.) Aufsatz. Zur Kenntnis der Gattung Gervaisia (Opisthandria). Zoologischer Anzeiger. 30(24):790–822.
- VERHOEFF KW. 1921. Über Diplopoden der Riviera und einige alpenländische Chilognathen (92. Diplopoden-Aufsatz). Archiv für Naturgeschichte. 87A(2):1–110.
- VERHOEFF KW. 1926. Chilognathen-Beiträge (103. Diplopoden-Aufsatz). Zoologischer Anzeiger. 68(3–4):109–127. Leipzig
- VERHOEFF KW. 1929. Zur Systematik, vergleichenden Morphologie und Geographie europäischer Diplopoden, zugleich ein zoogeographischer Beitrag. (111. Diplopoden-Aufsatz). Zoologische Jahrbücher, Abteilung für Systematik, Ökologie und Geographie der Tiere. 57:555–659.
- VERHOEFF KW. 1932. Diplopoden-Beiträge (124. Diplopoden-Aufsatz). Zoologische Jahrbücher, Abteilung für Systematik, Ökologie und Geographie der Tiere. 62(5–6):469–524.
- VERHOEFF KW. 1941. Asiatische Beiträge V, VI. Revue de la Faculté des Sciences de l'Université d'Istanbul. 6:278–318.
- VUČKOVIĆ Z. 1956. Prilog proučavanju faune stonoga (Myriapoda) severne Srbije i Vojvodine. Zbornik Matice Srpske, Serija prirodnih nauka. 10:1–7.
- VUJIĆ V, ILIĆ B, JOVANOVIĆ Z, PAVKOVIĆ-LUČIĆ S, SELAKOVIĆ S, TOMIĆ V, LUČIĆ L. 2018. Sexual behaviour and morphological variation in the millipede *Megaphyllum bosniense* (Verhoeff, 1897). Contributions to Zoology. 87(3):133–148.